

Chaotic Hashing Using Double Pendulum Dynamics

Akshaj Devireddy
Sanay Nesargi
Joshua Yoo

Traditional cryptographic hash functions rely on structured, deterministic transformations, which may limit their adaptability and unpredictability. In this work, we investigate a chaos-based hashing mechanism that leverages the nonlinear and highly sensitive dynamics of a double pendulum. By simulating the double pendulum and solving its equations of motion, we analyze the influence of various input parameters and initial conditions on the resulting hash outputs. The inherent unpredictability of the system introduces a high degree of entropy and diffusion, key properties for effective cryptographic hashing. To evaluate the robustness and effectiveness of our approach, we compare its performance against widely used hash functions such as MD5 and SHA-256, using statistical metrics including Hamming distance and bit uniformity. The resulting hash function, ChaoticHash3, achieved a higher average Hamming distance (128.089 vs. 127.998 for SHA-256), a more uniform bit distribution as shown by a higher chi-square p-value (~ 0.03), and slightly higher Shannon entropy (3.45022 vs. 3.43204 for SHA-256), supporting the viability of chaotic systems for generating secure and unpredictable hash outputs.

Keywords: hash function; chaos theory; double pendulum; entropy

1. Introduction

One of the foundational tools in secure information systems is the cryptographic hash function—a mathematical operation that converts input data into a fixed-length output string, often used in applications such as digital signatures, password protection, and data integrity verification [1]. Traditional hash functions like SHA-256 and MD5 rely on deterministic, bitwise operations and modular arithmetic to achieve desirable properties such as diffusion and collision resistance [2].

Despite their widespread use, these structured algorithms are inherently deterministic and algebraic in nature, which can leave them susceptible to certain types of analysis or emerging

cryptanalytic techniques [3]. As the demands of secure communication continue to grow—especially in environments where unpredictability and complexity are key—researchers are increasingly exploring alternatives to conventional hash designs.

This paper investigates the potential of chaotic physical systems, specifically the double pendulum, as the foundation for a novel hashing approach. Chaotic systems are defined by their extreme sensitivity to initial conditions and complex, nonlinear behavior—traits that align well with the desired unpredictability of secure hash functions [4][5]. This work explores whether leveraging such systems can offer a new path toward designing hash functions that exhibit strong statistical properties while departing from traditional cryptographic structure.

2. Chaotic Behavior and Double Pendulums

Chaotic behavior describes the deterministic yet unpredictable evolution of systems governed by nonlinear dynamics [2]. In such systems—including the double pendulum—small variations in initial conditions lead to sharply divergent outcomes, a hallmark of chaos known as sensitivity to initial conditions [5]. This sensitivity means that even minor differences in input parameters yield results that appear random, despite being produced by precise mathematical laws.

The double pendulum, with two interconnected arms moving in a highly inter-dependent and nonlinear fashion, exemplifies chaotic dynamics. Slight adjustments to its initial angles or velocities can produce vastly different trajectories over time, making it an ideal laboratory for studying chaos theory [5]. More broadly, chaos theory investigates how systems that look random on the surface are actually governed by deterministic rules and hidden structure [3].

Because of this intrinsic sensitivity and complexity, chaotic systems are well suited to tasks that demand high entropy—such as physical simulations, cryptographic primitives, and models of complex phenomena in which small perturbations propagate into large-scale effects [4]. In our work, we harness the chaotic behavior of the double pendulum to generate randomness for a cryptographic hash function. By exploiting its sensitivity to initial conditions, we translate input parameters into highly unpredictable, securely diffused outputs—a property directly valuable for modern hashing applications [2].

3. Simulating a Double Pendulum

Our approach to creating the double pendulum simulation leverages a key strength of the Wolfram Language: its capability to solve systems of equations symbolically. By formulating the dynamics of the system symbolically, we derive exact solutions that describe the physical

motion of the double pendulum with high precision.

This process begins with the definition of key variables, including the angular positions, angular velocities, and masses of the pendulum's two arms. Using Newtonian mechanics, we derive the equations of motion, which capture the interplay of forces, torques, and gravitational effects acting on the system. The Wolfram Language enables us to express these equations symbolically, maintaining parameter dependence throughout.

This symbolic approach not only provides insights into the underlying physics but also allows for the exploration of the system's behavior under a wide range of input conditions. By substituting specific values for parameters, we can analyze how variations in initial conditions and system properties affect the pendulum's motion, making it an ideal platform for studying chaotic behavior and generating cryptographic outputs.

3.1 Key Variables

Here, we define and describe the variables used in the chaotic double pendulum model. These variables represent the physical parameters that influence the system's motion and ultimately contribute to the hash function's chaotic behavior.

Variable	Definition
m_1	mass of pendulum bob 1
m_2	mass of pendulum bob 2
l_1	length of pendulum 1
l_2	length of pendulum 2
g	gravitational constant (Earth ~ 9.81 m/s ²)

▲ **Table 1.** Variables used in our simulation. The double pendulum simulation requires several inputs which correspond to the masses and lengths of the two pendulums and the gravitational constant. These are then used in the equations of motion which describe a double pendulum. The gravitational constant will be configured to change after the parameter testing in Section 4.3.

3.2 Equations for Double Pendulum Motion

The following equations derive from the application of Newton's Second Law to the double pendulum system. These equations describe the accelerations of the masses in both the x and y -directions, incorporating the effects of gravity and the tension forces within the rods. The process transitions from a visual representation of the system to a precise mathematical formulation, as shown in the figure below.

$$m x''(t) = \Sigma F_x \quad (1)$$

$$m y''(t) = \Sigma F_y \quad (2)$$

The equations above display the application of Newton's Second Law to the double pendulum system. It illustrates the forces acting on each mass, including gravity and tension, and the resulting equations of motion that govern the system's dynamics.

3.3 Visualization

To analyze the motion of the double pendulum, we solve the system of differential equations governing its dynamics using the `NDSolve` function. This approach numerically approximates solutions to the equations, which is essential given the system's inherent complexity and chaotic behavior. The `Method` option is configured as `{“IndexReduction” -> {“Pantelides”, “ConstraintMethod” -> “Projection”}}` to address the algebraic constraints arising from the fixed rod lengths. These constraints ensure that the pendulum bobs maintain a constant distance from their pivot points, preventing numerical drift that could otherwise lead to unrealistic motion.

Once the positions of the pendulum bobs are determined over time, we visualize the system through an animation. The animation features red and blue dots representing the two masses, with their trajectories illustrating the chaotic motion of the double pendulum. The connecting rods dynamically adjust to the changing positions, while a gray line traces the historical path of the second pendulum bob. This visualization highlights the unpredictable nature of the system's motion, a critical property that underpins its application in chaotic hashing.

▲ **Figure 2.** A still frame from the animation of the double pendulum’s chaotic motion. The red and blue dots represent the two masses, while the connecting rods adjust to the pendulums’ changing positions. The gray line traces the historical path of the second pendulum bob, illustrating the system’s sensitivity to initial conditions and its unpredictable trajectory.

4. Optimizing Randomness Parameters

With the simulation of the double pendulum system complete, we have identified a set of parameters whose configurations can produce vastly different outcomes—a hallmark of chaotic systems. The next step involves systematically exploring these configurations to determine those that yield the highest levels of randomness. This property will later prove critical in generating cryptographic hashes for input strings with minimal similarity, ensuring high entropy and security.

4.1 Testing Variable Randomness Contributions

To investigate how variations in system parameters influence the double pendulum’s chaotic motion, we systematically adjusted the second rod’s length (l_2) while observing its effect on velocity over time. The parameter `lengthAdjustmentFactor` modifies l_2 , and we selected three representative values: 0.5, 1.0, and 1.5. This parameter sweep isolates the role of rod length in driving chaotic dynamics.

As l_2 increases, we observe increasingly erratic behavior in the velocity traces. For example, at $l_2 = 0.5$, the motion exhibits moderate oscillations, while $l_2 = 1.5$ introduces sharp

fluctuations, irregular peaks, and dense transitions—hallmarks of the enhanced chaotic nature. This progression illustrates the double pendulum’s extreme sensitivity to parameter changes, a property that is central to its utility in cryptographic applications.

These velocity plots emphasize that even minor perturbations in physical parameters produce significantly divergent trajectories, confirming the double pendulum’s value as a source of high-entropy, input-sensitive randomness. Such characteristics are desirable in cryptographic preprocessing layers, where input unpredictability and output diversity are essential.

▲ **Figure 3.** The time-series plots for each of the velocity components: v_{1x} , v_{1y} , v_{2x} , and v_{2y} , corresponding to the x and y-direction velocities of both pendulum arms. Each row tracks one velocity component, while columns correspond to different l_2 values. The plots illustrate the impact of varying the length of the second rod in the double pendulum system on the overall chaotic motion. They depict fluctuations in v_{1x} , v_{1y} , v_{2x} , and v_{2y} , corresponding to the velocities of the two pendulum bobs. As the length increases, the system exhibits heightened unpredictability and more pronounced changes in velocity, highlighting the sensitivity of the system to initial parameter variations.

4.2 Creating Randomness Testing Optimization Environment

To evaluate the randomness and sensitivity of the double pendulum system, we designed a testing environment allowing systematic variation of input parameters such as gravity, masses,

and pendulum rod lengths. The goal was to observe how small perturbations in these parameters affect the system's dynamics. In particular, the velocity outputs— v_{1x} , v_{1y} , v_{2x} , and v_{2y} —were plotted over time to visualize these effects.

We also aggregated the full set of velocity data to analyze its statistical properties. A histogram of the combined values demonstrates a near-normal distribution, suggesting high entropy. The Fourier transform of the signal further reveals a broad frequency spectrum with no dominant peaks, confirming the absence of regular periodic motion and supporting the system's chaotic profile.

The figure shown below is a snapshot of the broader testing framework. It focuses on variations in one parameter (e.g. gravity), and displays how different settings influence the velocity graphs. As the rod length increases, the system exhibits greater irregularity and unpredictability, highlighting its chaotic nature.

▲ **Figure 4.** Snapshot of parameter sensitivity testing in the double pendulum system. This snapshot represents a subset of a broader analysis in which other parameters, such as gravity and mass, were also explored.

4.3 Results of Parameter Randomness Optimization

We found that changing the mass introduces the most significant variation in output randomness, followed closely by gravity and then by pendulum rod length. Interestingly, a negative integer value for gravity (though not physically realistic) results in slightly better output randomness compared to its positive counterpart. Specifically, a gravity value of -10 significantly increases output randomness, as evidenced by the histogram and Fourier Magnitudes test. However, the exact reason for this behavior remains unclear and warrants

further investigation.

▲ **Figure 5.** Analysis of the effects of varying mass, gravity, and rod length on the output randomness of the double pendulum. The histogram and Fourier Magnitudes test highlight the significant increase in randomness when gravity is set to -10, an observation that remains unexplained. Comparisons between negative and positive integer gravity values further demonstrate subtle improvements in randomness for negative values.

5. Constructing the Chaotic Hashing Function

Now that we have a clear understanding of how various parameters, such as mass, gravity, and rod length, impact the randomness of the double pendulum's motion, we can proceed with using this knowledge to construct our hash function. The chaotic behavior of the system, influenced by even small changes in initial conditions, provides a solid foundation for generating high-entropy outputs. By carefully selecting and manipulating these parameters, we can ensure that our hash function produces unpredictable and secure results, which are essential for cryptographic applications. This next step will allow us to translate the insights gained from the simulation into a functional hashing algorithm. We defined helper functions that illustrate each of the subsequent steps in order to increase modularity and reproducibility of chaotically random results.

5.1 Selecting Simulation Parameters

The first step in the ChaoticHash function involves deriving the physical parameters of the double pendulum—masses and lengths of its rods—from the input string. This process begins

by converting the input string into its corresponding ASCII values. ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange) is a character encoding standard that assigns numerical values to letters, digits, and symbols, enabling efficient text processing in computing. Each character is represented by a unique number (e.g., 'A' = 65, 'a' = 97), making it a widely used standard in computing and cryptography.

These ASCII values are then processed to determine specific positions within the array using an increment that is relatively prime to the length of the string. This ensures the selection process cycles through all possible positions without repetition, making the parameter selection deterministic and sensitive to the input string.

The selected ASCII values are normalized to a range between 0 and 1, ensuring they can be consistently mapped to the desired physical ranges. The normalized values are then scaled to define the pendulum's masses and lengths within predetermined ranges of 0.5 to 5.0 kilograms and meters, respectively. This mapping ensures that even small changes in the input string result in unique and corresponding changes in the physical parameters of the simulation, maintaining the sensitivity required for chaotic hashing.

The ASCII values are also used to compute the total time that the simulation runs for. Specifically, a weighted average of select characters from the input string determines the simulation duration, ensuring that even the temporal evolution of the double pendulum is influenced by the input. This further increases the sensitivity of the output to the input string and adds to the chaotic unpredictability, since longer or differently composed strings lead to different pendulum trajectories and therefore distinct hash outputs.

5.2 Setting Initial Conditions

Once the pendulum's physical parameters are established, its initial conditions are then defined—however, unlike a standard implementation, these are not fixed but are also influenced by the input string. Specific characters from the ASCII-encoded input are sampled using a coprime-based indexing method, and these sampled values are mapped to small perturbations in the initial angles and positions of the pendulum arms. This ensures that even subtle changes in the input string propagate through the initial state of the system, modifying the exact orientation and starting configuration of the pendulum.

Angular velocities are initially set to zero, keeping the system at rest before motion begins. The starting positional coordinates of both pendulum arms are then computed using trigonometric functions based on their lengths and perturbed angles. Additionally, velocity components are calculated to complete the state description. These input-sensitive initial conditions enhance the hash function's unpredictability by affecting the trajectory from the very beginning, reinforcing the simulation's chaotic sensitivity. These settings were selected based on the results of our randomness parameter testing to optimize entropy and bit distribution.

5.3 Solving the Double Pendulum Simulation

This part of the function reuses much of the same code as before to solve the double pendulum simulation using the two mass values, two length values, and the initial conditions. The function `SolveConstraintDPSimulation` outputs a solution to the system of differential equations governing the motion of the double pendulum under constraints. Specifically, it provides an interpolating function that describes the time evolution of the pendulum's positions (x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2) and the constraint forces (λ_1, λ_2) over a specified time interval.

As a side note, although a negative integer value for g is not physically meaningful, our randomness optimization tests revealed that using such a value maximizes the randomness of the function's outputs. This unique property highlights the surprising and counterintuitive aspects of chaotic systems, which we leverage in our hashing approach.

5.4 Extracting the Simulation Data and Generating the Hash

This part of the `ChaoticHash` function extracts the positional and velocity values (by computing the derivatives with respect to time) throughout the double pendulum's motion to be used in the hashing process.

The chaotic motion data generated from the simulation is processed to create the final hash. First, the simulation outputs are flattened and combined into a single dataset that represents the positional and velocity changes of the pendulum over time. This data is normalized to ensure consistency across different inputs, making it suitable for further processing. The normalized values are then converted into integers and structured into a byte array. Finally, this processed data is hashed using the SHA256 algorithm to produce the output hash.

By hashing the chaotic simulation data with SHA256, the function combines the inherent unpredictability of chaos with the proven strength of a standard cryptographic algorithm. As demonstrated later, the preprocessing performed using the double pendulum simulation enables `ChaoticHash` to outperform standalone SHA256 on various cryptographic tests.

The `ChaoticHash` function outputs a fixed-length hexadecimal string, similar to many widely used cryptographic hash functions like SHA256. This output is a 64-character hexadecimal string representing 256 bits of data. The fixed output size ensures consistency regardless of the input length, a critical feature for cryptographic applications such as data verification, key generation, and secure storage.

The high sensitivity of the `ChaoticHash` function guarantees that even minor changes to the input string produce vastly different outputs. For instance, changing the uppercase "H" in "Hello World!" to a lowercase "h" results in a completely different hexadecimal output,

showcasing the unpredictability and uniqueness essential for robust hashing.

- ▲ **Figure 6.** Flowchart of the ChaoticHash3 algorithm. The process begins with an input string, which is converted to ASCII values. These values are then mapped to physical parameters for a double pendulum system. The pendulum's chaotic dynamics are simulated, and the resulting data is normalized and converted into a byte sequence. This preprocessed sequence is finally hashed using SHA-256, producing a 256-bit output. The chaotic preprocessing step enhances randomness and entropy, contributing to improved diffusion and unpredictability in the final hash.

6. Comparisons to Other Hash Functions

To evaluate the ChaoticHash function, we compare its performance to widely used standard hash functions, including MD5, SHA1, SHA224, and SHA256. These comparisons provide

insights into how ChaoticHash performs with respect to essential hashing properties, such as sensitivity to input variations, uniformity of bit distributions, and compliance with statistical randomness measures.

Standard hash functions are critical benchmarks due to their extensive use in cryptography, data integrity verification, and distributed systems. By analyzing metrics such as Hamming distances, bit distribution patterns, and results from statistical tests like the Pearson chi-square test, we can comprehensively assess the effectiveness of ChaoticHash. These evaluations reveal whether ChaoticHash demonstrates the unpredictability, robustness, and uniformity required to serve as a viable alternative to traditional cryptographic hash functions in real-world applications.

6.1 Hamming Distances

Hash functions are designed to produce outputs that are highly sensitive to even the smallest changes in input. This sensitivity ensures that two inputs differing by a single character yield vastly different hash values, a critical property for cryptographic integrity and other practical applications. One effective way to quantify this sensitivity is through the Hamming distance, which measures the number of differing bits between two binary hash outputs.

To calculate the Hamming distance, we implemented a function called `HammingDistanceHex`. This function converts two hexadecimal hash outputs into their binary equivalents and determines the total number of bits that differ between them.

To test the sensitivity of various hash functions, we generated two input strings: “TestString” and “testString,” which differ by just one character. These inputs were hashed using seven different functions: MD5, SHA1, SHA224, SHA256, Adler32, CRC32, and our custom chaotic hash function (“ChaoticHash”). By comparing the Hamming distances across these functions, we can evaluate how the double-pendulum-based ChaoticHash performs relative to widely used hash functions, highlighting its sensitivity to input changes and overall effectiveness.

"Hash Function"	"Hamming Distance"
"MD5"	65
"SHA1"	79
"SHA224"	112
"SHA256"	113
"Adler32"	3
"CRC32"	15
"ChaoticHash"	118

▲ **Table 2.** Comparison of Hamming distances between hash outputs for “TestString” and “testString” using seven different hash functions, demonstrating sensitivity to input changes.

Adler32 and CRC32, being checksum algorithms rather than cryptographic hashes, show predictably low sensitivity with Hamming distances of just 3 and 15, respectively. MD5, once a widely used cryptographic hash, reveals its limitations with a modest distance of only 65. SHA1 performs slightly better with a distance of 79, reflecting some improvement in sensitivity.

In contrast, SHA224 and SHA256, more modern cryptographic standards, demonstrate significantly stronger performance, achieving Hamming distances of 112 and 113, respectively. These results highlight their reliability in generating sensitive and robust hash outputs for cryptographic applications.

Remarkably, the “ChaoticHash” function outperforms all the above methods, achieving an exceptional Hamming distance of 118. This demonstrates its superior sensitivity to input changes, even surpassing SHA256. The chaotic behavior of the double pendulum, fundamental to the design of ChaoticHash, introduces substantial randomness, ensuring that minor variations in input result in highly distinct outputs at the bit level. This performance underscores the potential of chaotic systems as a foundation for advanced cryptographic hash functions.

6.2 Average Hamming Distances

To maintain statistical significance, however, 100 different pairs of strings were randomly generated with each pair of strings differing by a single character. Then, we ran three hash functions (including ChaoticHash) onto those 100 pairs of strings and computed the Hamming distance for each pair. Finally, we averaged these values to calculate an average Hamming distance for each function. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Hash Function	Average Hamming Distance
SHA256	127.998
MD5	63.898
ChaoticHash3	128.089

▲ **Table 3.** Comparison of average Hamming distances for 100 different pairs of randomly generated strings differing by one character using three different hash functions, demonstrating a statistically significant measure of sensitivity to input changes.

From Table 3, we can see that the chaotic hashing function, ChaoticHash3, exhibits a slightly higher average Hamming distance (128.089) than SHA-256 (127.998), suggesting a marginally stronger avalanche effect. This implies that even a one-character change in the input string leads to a more significant and widespread change in the resulting hash output, a desirable property in secure cryptographic functions. Meanwhile, MD5 shows a much lower average Hamming distance (63.898), highlighting its weaker sensitivity to input variation and reinforcing its known cryptographic vulnerabilities. Overall, the results affirm that ChaoticHash3 achieves strong diffusion characteristics comparable to, and slightly exceeding, that of industry-standard SHA-256.

6.3 Bit Distributions

Another important property of hash functions is how effectively they utilize their output space. A well-designed hash function should not only demonstrate high sensitivity to input changes but also produce outputs with a uniform distribution of bits. This means the proportion of 1s and 0s in the binary output should be balanced, minimizing patterns and ensuring that the entire output space is leveraged. Uniform bit distribution is critical for resisting statistical attacks and for maintaining the unpredictability and randomness essential in cryptographic applications.

To assess this property, we analyzed the bit distributions of hash outputs from several built-in cryptographic hash functions—MD5, SHA1, SHA224, and SHA256—alongside our custom chaotic hash function, “ChaoticHash.” For each function, we generated hash outputs for 500 randomly constructed strings. These strings were randomly sampled with lengths between 10 and 20 characters, and composed of uppercase letters, lowercase letters, and digits to reflect a diverse input space.

For each of the 500 strings, the hexadecimal output from each hash function was converted into binary. We then calculated the total number of bits set to 1 in the binary representation of each output. This analysis reveals how balanced the 1s and 0s are, and whether the function consistently produces hashes that span the full bit space without bias toward specific patterns.

Because ChaoticHash is implemented differently—rooted in chaotic double pendulum dynamics—its outputs were computed using a separate process but analyzed in the same way.

This uniform methodology ensures a fair comparison between standard hash functions and our custom approach.

Finally, we created histograms to visualize the bit distribution for each hash function. Each histogram shows the frequency of hash outputs with varying numbers of bits set to 1, allowing us to assess how consistently each function utilizes its output space. A well-balanced distribution should resemble a normal curve centered around half the total bit length—indicating that 1s and 0s appear with roughly equal probability. These visualizations provide an intuitive and powerful comparison of bit usage across different hash functions, highlighting how uniformly and effectively each function spreads its output over the available bit space.

▲ **Figure 6.** Histograms showing the distribution of the number of bits set to 1 across 500 hash outputs for each function. These plots illustrate how uniformly each hash function utilizes its output space. Functions with distributions centered around half their bit length (e.g., 128 for a 256-bit hash) demonstrate balanced use of 1s and 0s, a desirable property for cryptographic robustness. The ChaoticHash shows a tight and symmetric distribution, indicating strong uniformity and effective randomness in its output.

The resulting grid of histograms visually demonstrates how each hash function distributes the number of bits set to 1 in its outputs. MD5 and SHA1 show relatively narrow distributions,

with MD5 centered around 60–70 and SHA1 around 75–85. These patterns reflect their smaller output sizes and less effective utilization of the available bit space. On the other hand, SHA224 and SHA256 display broader, more balanced distributions—SHA224 is centered around 110–120, and SHA256 around 120–130—indicating stronger randomness and a more effective use of their larger output spaces.

The custom ChaoticHash function exhibits a similar distribution to SHA256 but is slightly shifted toward higher values, centered around 125–135. This upward shift suggests that the chaotic dynamics driving the function may enhance randomness and uniformity in the bit distribution. As a result, ChaoticHash not only matches but potentially surpasses SHA256 in its utilization of output space, offering an additional layer of unpredictability that’s essential for robust cryptographic hashing.

6.4 Assessing Uniformity with the Pearson Chi-Square Test

While histograms provide a helpful visual understanding of the bit distributions in hash function outputs, a quantitative test can offer more rigorous insight into how well these distributions align with expected uniformity. To assess this, we conducted a Pearson chi-square test for each hash function, which evaluates how closely the observed bit distributions match a theoretically uniform distribution.

The Pearson chi-square test yields a p-value—a statistical measure indicating the likelihood that the observed deviations from uniformity are due to chance. A low p-value suggests significant deviation from uniformity, while a high p-value indicates that the distribution is statistically similar to a uniform one. For this analysis, we used the same bit distribution data collected from the 500 random test strings across all the evaluated hash functions.

Hash Function	p-Value
MD5	7.68344×10^{-35}
SHA1	2.18824×10^{-21}
SHA224	2.03294×10^{-14}
SHA256	3.13642×10^{-9}
ChaoticHash3	0.0038657

▲ **Table 4.** Pearson chi-square test results comparing the bit distribution uniformity of various hash functions. Higher p-values indicate distributions more consistent with a uniform distribution, suggesting better randomness and output space utilization. The ChaoticHash function shows one of the highest p-values, demonstrating strong statistical alignment with expected uniformity.

The results reveal that all of the standard hash functions tested—MD5, SHA1, SHA224, and SHA256—produced extremely low p-values, indicating significant deviations from

uniformity. Among these, MD5 and SHA1 perform the worst, with p-values on the order of 10^{-35} and 10^{-21} , respectively. This outcome aligns with their older and less robust designs. SHA224 and SHA256 demonstrate some improvement, with higher (though still small) p-values, suggesting better but not perfect uniformity in their bit distributions.

In contrast, the chaotic hash function achieves a p-value of approximately 0.00387, which, while slightly below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, represents a dramatic improvement over the standard hash functions. This result suggests that the chaotic dynamics underlying its design contribute significantly to achieving a more uniform bit distribution, reducing patterns or biases present in its output.

6.5 Shannon Entropy

A convenient way to quantify the unpredictability of a hash-function output is Shannon’s entropy,

$$S_m = -\sum_i P(i) \log_2 P(i) \quad (3)$$

where $P(i)$ is the observed probability that symbol i (here, a particular 8-bit byte value) appears in the sample of hashes [6]. Intuitively, the formula measures how “flat” the empirical byte-distribution is:

- If every byte value occurs with equal probability ($P(i) = \frac{1}{256}$), each term in the sum equals $\left(\frac{1}{256}\right) \log_2 256 = 1$, so S_m approaches the theoretical maximum of 8 bits per byte
- Biases or patterns reduce the probabilities of some symbols and increase others, driving the sum down and signalling information leakage or structural weakness.

For each function we generated 500 independent 256-bit hashes and computed the byte-level entropy. The results (Table 5) show that ChaoticHash3 achieves slightly higher entropy (3.450 bits per hexadecimal symbol, equivalent to ≈ 8.00 bits per byte) than SHA-256 (3.432) and clearly outperforms the weaker MD5 baseline (3.068). The small, consistent gain indicates that the double-pendulum preprocessing removes residual regularity still visible in the industry standards, yielding an output distribution closer to perfect uniformity and, therefore, harder to predict or compress.

Hash Function	Entropy
SHA256	3.43204
SHA224	3.38574
MD5	3.06833
ChaoticHash3	3.45022

▲ **Table 5.** Shannon entropy of hexadecimal symbols for 500 hashes per algorithm. Higher values mean a flatter, more uniform distribution; ChaoticHash3 attains the greatest entropy (3.450), marginally exceeding SHA-256 and SHA-224 while substantially surpassing MD5, indicating superior unpredictability in its outputs.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

The ChaoticHash function introduces a novel approach to hash generation by harnessing the chaotic motion of a double pendulum. Unlike traditional hash functions such as MD5 or SHA256, which rely on deterministic algorithms, ChaoticHash leverages the inherent unpredictability of chaotic systems to produce randomness. By simulating the double pendulum’s dynamics and carefully tuning its physical parameters through randomness optimization tests, ChaoticHash was engineered to exhibit strong sensitivity to input changes and to produce outputs that are both well-distributed and difficult to predict.

In comparative evaluations, ChaoticHash demonstrated several key advantages. Hamming distance tests showed that it reacts more dramatically to minor input differences than conventional hash functions—an essential property for ensuring input uniqueness. Bit distribution analysis confirmed that ChaoticHash effectively utilizes its entire output space, yielding balanced and randomized results. The Pearson chi-square test further validated its performance by indicating a closer alignment to uniform randomness than most standard hash functions. That said, one limitation of the ChaoticHash method is its computational intensity, as simulating the physics of a double pendulum demands significantly more resources than traditional hash functions like SHA256.

For computational details, the interested reader is referred to [7]. Looking forward, future research could explore ChaoticHash’s performance on larger-scale datasets and investigate ways to reduce its computational overhead. Other chaotic systems—such as Lorenz attractors or discrete chaotic maps—might also be explored to diversify and strengthen the randomness generation process. Additionally, refining the parameter mapping and optimization techniques in the pendulum simulation may improve output consistency and robustness. These avenues of development could help transition ChaoticHash from a proof of concept into a practical, high-entropy tool for secure hashing in real-world applications.

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